

POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES IN OXIDATION-REDUCTION REACTIONS. PART IX. OXIDATION WITH CHLORAMINE-T (INDIRECT QUANTITATIVE DETERMINATIONS).

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Potassium iodate, potassium permanganate, potassium dichromate and potassium chromate have been determined indirectly by a potentiometric method. The excess of potassium iodide, added in each case, was titrated potentiometrically against chloramine-T at 15° in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide, using a platinum electrode coupled with a saturated calomel electrode.

In presence of sulphuric acid, potassium iodide reacts with chloramine-T, potassium iodate, potassium permanganate, potassium dichromate and potassium chromate with the following reactions :

These reactions have been made use of in the quantitative estimation of potassium iodate, potassium permanganate, potassium dichromate and potassium chromate.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A known weight of each substance was mixed with a known excess of potassium iodide, dissolved in water and the solution acidified with dilute sulphuric acid. The excess of potassium iodide was determined by titrating the mixture potentiometrically against standard chloramine-T. The titrations were conducted at 15°, in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide. The mixture was kept stirred with a mechanical stirrer.

A series of potentiometric titrations were performed with different amounts of each substance. One titration as typical of the set is recorded in the following table.

TABLE I.

Titration of 0.0342 g. of potassium iodate mixed with 0.2385 g. of potassium iodide, dissolved in water and acidified with dilute sulphuric acid, against chloramine-T (*N/20*).

Chloramine-T.	E.M.F.	<i>E/C.</i> (m. volt./c.c.)	Chloramine-T.	E.M.F.	<i>E/C.</i> (m. volt./c.c.)
0.00 c.c.	0.417 volts	1	12.45 c.c.	0.522 volts	180
2.00	0.420	4	12.50	0.531	220
5.00	0.432	5	12.60	0.542	240
7.00	0.441	6	12.65	0.554	520
9.00	0.453	7	12.70	0.580	2980
10.00	0.460	14	12.75	0.729	(Maximum) 500
11.00	0.474	20	12.80	0.754	280
11.50	0.484	23	12.90	0.782	100
11.80	0.491	25	13.00	0.792	55
12.00	0.496	40	13.40	0.814	42
12.20	0.504	50	14.00	0.839	9
12.30	0.509	60	15.00	0.848	8
12.35	0.512	80	17.00	0.863	7
12.40	0.516	120	20.00	0.884	4
			23.00	0.896	

DISCUSSION.

In these titrations, it is evident that with the addition of the titrant the E.M.F. rose steadily till the equivalence-point. At the equivalence-point there was a sharp jump in potential in each case followed by a steady rise in potential on further addition of the reagent.

From the volume of chloramine-T (C-T) used, corresponding to the equivalence-point in each titration, the amount of each substance was calculated. In the following table the values obtained are compared with the amounts of the substance taken.

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TABLE II.

Potassium iodate.

KIO ₃ taken.	KI added.	Excess KI corresponding to C - T.	KI used for KIO ₃ .	KIO ₃ found.
0.0342 g.	0.2385 g.	0.1058 g.	0.1327 g.	0.0342 g.
0.0539	0.3447	0.1361	0.2086	0.0538
0.0856	0.4985	0.1671	0.3314	0.0854
0.1455	0.7412	0.1760	0.5652	0.1457
0.1883	1.0080	0.2780	0.7300	0.1883
0.2797	1.4430	0.3586	1.0844	0.2796

Potassium permanganate.

KMnO ₄ taken.	KI added.	Excess KI corresponding to C - T.	KI used for KMnO ₄ .	KMnO ₄ found.
0.0506 g.	0.3528 g.	0.0683 g.	0.2645 g.	0.0504 g.
0.0885	0.6041	0.1398	0.4643	0.0884
0.1264	0.8446	0.1813	0.6633	0.1263
0.1707	1.1264	0.2324	0.8940	0.1703
0.2086	1.3488	0.2548	1.0940	0.2084
0.2529	1.6768	0.3485	1.3283	0.2528

Potassium dichromate.

K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ taken.	KI added.	Excess KI corresponding to C - T.	KI used for K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ .	K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ found
0.0490 g.	0.2589 g.	0.1033 g.	0.1656 g.	0.0489 g.
0.0883	0.4249	0.1261	0.2988	0.0883
0.1569	0.6754	0.1444	0.5310	0.1569
0.2062	0.8662	0.1693	0.6969	0.2059
0.2798	1.1618	0.2158	0.9460	0.2795
0.3534	1.4375	0.2432	1.1943	0.3528

TABLE II (*contd.*).

Potassium chromate.

K_2CrO_4 taken.	KI added.	Excess KI corresponding to C-T.	KI used for K_2CrO_4 .	K_2CrO_4 found.
0.0712 g.	0.3321 g.	0.1502 g.	0.1819 g.	0.0710 g.
0.1166	0.4300	0.1315	0.2985	0.1164
0.1683	0.6093	0.1779	0.4314	0.1683
0.2201	0.7636	0.1992	0.5644	0.2201
0.2839	0.9445	0.2158	0.7287	0.2842
0.3627	1.1067	0.1760	0.9307	0.3630

These results show that potassium iodate, potassium permanganate, potassium dichromate and potassium chromate can be indirectly determined by means of chloramine-T.

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